

DEVELOPMENT OF MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE RECLAMATION OF PASTURES

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Annotation. 0‘51% of the total land area of the Republic of Uzbekistan is pastures and hayfields. There are more than 1,700 plant species used as fodder in pastures and groves. Pastures and hayfields play an important role in providing livestock with nutritious fodder and in producing high-quality, low-cost products. Therefore, partial or radical reclamation of existing pastures and hayfields in the country, increase of soil fertility, creation of a positive ecological situation, preservation and reproduction of pasture plants by species, livestock breeding on irrigated lands Establishment of irrigated cultural pastures on specialized farms, improvement of grazing technologies in them, adequate feeding of livestock in natural and cultural pastures, scientific use of pastures and hayfields. future q loq farming specialists should have in-depth knowledge. This textbook is based on the program "Pasture reclamation" adopted in accordance with the "State Education Standard" by Associate Professors of the Department of "Fundamentals of Agriculture and Land Reclamation" Tashkent State University U.N. Orkulov, H. Sheraliyev, Zh. Written by Q ochk rov s. During the preparation of the textbook, the authors obtained information from the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Institute of Animal Husbandry and Ecology of Uzbekistan. From the results of scientific research work of the Uzbek Livestock Research Institute and scientists working in the country, IV Larin's "L ugovodstvo ip astb ishnoye khozyaystvo." U .N orqu lov, H .S hera liyevn ing "Q ishloq x o‘ ja l ig I amelioration "textbooks.

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Introduction. In all countries of the world, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, the situation with natural resources and their rational use in the XXI century remains relevant at the national and global levels. Article 55 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Land, subsoil resources, water, flora and fauna and other natural resources are national wealth, must be used wisely and are under state protection." According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On the world of wire and its use", "On farming", "Dehkan farm" In the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On water and water use" and the Cabinet of Ministers No. 343 "On the state of flora of the Republic of Uzbekistan" Regulations on the Procedure for Maintaining the Cadastre "and Regulations and Resolutions No. 496" On Land Monitoring "contain the rules for the protection and rational use of land, water and flora and fauna. As of January 1, 2021, the total land area of the Republic of Uzbekistan is 44896.9 thousand hectares, of which 50.93% are pastures and thorns, 9.5% are irrigated arable land, 1.85% of arable land, 1.32% of arable land, 2.29% of forests, 0.85% of perennial forests and 32.38% of land not used for agriculture. 0 The Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the countries in the world with the largest flora. There are 4,500 higher plants in our country - 300 algae and more than 2,000 species of fungi *. Use of Uzbek plant resources for 350 types of food, 1700 types of fodder, 600 types of medicines, 650 types of essential oils, 150 types of dyes, 270 types of ornaments, 400 types of additives and 100 types of sapons possible. Pastures and hayfields cover 50.93% of the country's total area, and most of the available plant resources, 1,700 species, are used for fodder production. Therefore, it is important to improve the soil conditions of pastures and meadows, to maintain the accuracy of the existing vegetation cover by species, to increase productivity.

The northern boundaries of the Central Asian plain extend from the Styurt Plateau and the Aral Sea to Lake Balkhash, from the south and east to the foothills of the Pamirs, Alay, Tien Shan, Kopetog *, and from the west to the Caspian Sea. lands. About 70% of the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is located in the plains, which includes Kyzylkum, Ustyurt, Mirzachoi, Sherabad, Karshi. The relief

of the Ch oi region is very complex and diverse. Climatic conditions. The climatic conditions of the plains are close to the dry subtropical climate, the average temperature is + 18 ° C, the average temperature in the hottest July is + 58 ° C, and the coldest January is -15 ° C. does.

Atmospheric precipitation varies over many years, ranging from 75 mm to 200 mm. Precipitation falls mainly in winter and early spring, with almost no precipitation in summer and autumn. The air is extremely dry, with a humidity of 20-30%. It snows a lot and its cover does not exceed 5-10 cm, but it is stored for a very short time. Bugianish is 1800-2000 mm. Soil conditions. In the plains, brown soils, bald and barren, sandy loam soils and sandy loam soils are common. Brown soils are found in Ustyurt, Kyzylkum, Karshi, Qomop, Sherabad and other regions of the region. Brown soils are divided into the following types: saline plain brown soils, saline brown soils, gypsum soils, bald saline brown soils. Brown soils are saline, with water-soluble salts ranging from 0.3% to 2% in different soil layers, and salts with more than 2-3%. There are also gypsum layers at a depth of 10-70 cm in dark brown soils. Because reddish-brown soils are formed in parent rocks of different composition, their mechanical composition is also different, but more sandy and light sands are found. Humus, nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium are low in brown soils, humus is 0.2-0.8%, nitrogen is 0.02-0.006%, phosphorus is 0.09-0.15%, potassium 0.20-1.82% is mobile phosphorus 2.0-35.5 mg / kg and mobile potassium is 9.0-250 mg / kg (Table 1.3.1). The natural conditions of pastures determine the geographical condition of the pastures. Depending on the ameliorative condition of pastures, water and wind erosion, soil displacement, landslides, avalanches, sand migration, soil compaction and flooding, floods, wire cover, if the level of pasture use has a significant impact. It is known that pastures have different natural conditions in different regions. Therefore, the above-mentioned unfavorable factors are distributed in different soils along the ridges and they affect the reclamation condition of pastures.

Region	Existing natural discomfort factors
Mountain	Water erosion, foraging, land and avalanches, floods.
Adir	Water erosion, partial salinization of feed and swamping, drought.
Plain	Wind erosion, sand migration, land salinity and swamping, drought.
Coast	Swamping and salinization of the land, flood flow.

Causes of deterioration of the reclamation of plains in the plains Wind erosion. Sham ol e roz iya is widespread in the Uzbek region of Uzbekistan, and the total area of its pastures, according to the Institute of "Zdavyerloyiha", is 18,125,000 hectares. Wind erosion occurs in the middle and lower reaches of the Amu Darya, in the natural pastures of Bukhara, Navoi, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya regions and in the desert areas of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Candle erosion erodes the topsoil's humus-rich, nutrient-rich layer under the influence of candles moving across the earth's surface on a wide front. At the same time, under the influence of wind, the roots of plants growing in natural pastures are blown out or become unfit for germination, and during the dry season, the leaves and foliage grow. It has a strong negative effect on the process of flowering, fertilization and ripening. In addition, the moisture content of the soil increases rapidly under the influence of wind, resulting in a decrease in the total moisture reserves in the soil and a sharp decline in plant growth, development and productivity. Wind erosion is more common in areas with light mechanical sands, sands with low natural fertility, and low vegetation cover. Wind erosion has been observed to increase the amount of humus in the soil by 2-6 m per hectare, and a 2-3 m decrease in various mineral nutrients.

Factors to consider when evaluating pastures

- 1 In which reclamation zone is the pasture located.
- 2 Yielding area (in terms of ha) and pasture use coefficient (ratio of total pastures to the area actually used by pastures).
- 3 Pasture boundaries (forest trees, mountains and hills, cliffs, etc.).
- 4 Distance from farm to pasture and irrigation source, water supply.
- 5 Climatic conditions (duration of the growing season, average annual temperature, amount of precipitation).
- 6 Soil type mechanical composition, water-physical properties, agrochemical properties, lethal structure of the soil, salinity, swamp erosion levels, depth of groundwater, mineralization flow, salinity (natural and artificial).
- 7 Relief (macro, meso, micro) Relativity of rocks and hills, length,
- 8 In the coastal zone, the upper, middle and lower reaches of the coast, the flow regime of rivers, the flood width of the high and low water period.
- 9 The composition of pastures is divided into 4 groups according to the area of hayfields and arable lands, forage lands: 1) widely cultivated; 2) limited; 3) reclamation; 4) generally processed.
- 10 Wire cover and their nutritional value (name of plants, which type of plant in the group is more or less, poisonous plants are specified separately) The type of weeds in the group is more than 10% of the total weeds if so.
- 11 Pasture grass yield (pasture and hay yields are considered separately).
- 12 The level of consumption of pasture grass by livestock (80-85% high quality pasture when grass is consumed, 75-80% good when consumed, medium when consumed 70-75% and medium and 55-65% is poor quality pasture when grasses are consumed). The level of pasture use will be assessed on a 100-point scale after the above factors have been studied.

The condition of the pastures	Feeding unit	Points
1 Rich pastures	1000-810	100-81

2 0 'average pastures	800-600	80-61
3 Poor pastures	600-410	60—+1
4 Extremely helpless	400-210	40-21
5 Unusable pasture	200-20	20-2

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